

KLASYFIKACJA KOMPETENCJI PRACOWNIKÓW DLA SPOŁECZNIE-ODPOWIEDZIALNYCH PRZEDSIĘBIORSTW PRZEMYSŁU PRZETWÓRCZEGO

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Streszczenie. W artykule badane klasyfikacji kompetencji pracowników społecznie odpowiedzialnych przedsiębiorstw przemysłu przetwórczego, które będą działać podstawą do określenia wskaźników i metod ich oceny. Ustalono, że od poziomu kompetencji i kwalifikacji pracowników zależy maksymalizacja zysku przedsiębiorstwa przy minimalnych kosztach. Stwierdzono, że jednym z najważniejszych zadań kierownictwa, jest wybór narzędzi do oceny kompetencji pracownika, więc do tego potrzebne jest zrozumienie klasyfikacji kompetencji pracownika społecznie odpowiedzialnych przedsiębiorstw i podkreślając je według funkcji. Wyróżnione różne funkcje klasyfikacji kompetencji pracowników, wyjaśniane istotę niektórych, a także uzupełnione o dostępnych nowych klasyfikacją objawami, które są spowodowane wymogami współczesności. Oferowane zaawansowana kompleksowa klasyfikacja kompetencji pracowników dostosowany do społecznie odpowiedzialnych przedsiębiorstw, funkcje klasyfikacji które: za uniwersalność (ogólne i zawodowe); w zakresie objawów (instrumentalne, interpersonalne, systemowe); w dyscyplinie specjalizacją (produkcyjne, organizacyjne, finansowe, gospodarcze, intelektualne, diagnostyczne, metodologiczne, psychologiczne i inne); z odpowiedzialnością społeczną (społeczne, innowacyjne, inwestycyjne i inne); według typu sytuacji do rozwiązania której stosuje się kompetencji (kompetencji, które stosuje się w celu rozwiązania planowanej sytuacji; kompetencje, które stosuje się w celu rozwiązania sytuacji losowej); poziom samodzielności kształtowania (proste, złożone); w cyklu szkolenia (kompetencje, które powstają w wyniku uzyskania wykształcenia średniego; kompetencje, które powstają w wyniku szkolnictwa wyższego); za etapem pracy (kompetencje na wczesnym etapie pracy, kompetencji na późniejszym etapie zatrudnienia); w zakresie rozwoju pracownika (wysoki, powyżej średni, średni, niski); w miejscu wystąpienia (w miejscu pracy, w wyniku przejścia szkoleń, warsztatów, kursów); według częstotliwości stosowania (okresowe, jednorazowe). Taka funkcja klasyfikacji, jak społeczna odpowiedzialność jest oddzielona w dodatkową ważną składową.

Słowa kluczowe: kompetencje, klasyfikacja kompetencji, pracownik, odpowiedzialność społeczna, przedsiębiorstwo, przemysł przetwórczym.

CLASSIFICATION OF COMPETENCIES OF EMPLOYEE FOR SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ENTERPRISES OF THE PROCESSING INDUSTRY

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Abstract. The article investigated the classification of competencies of employees of socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry, which will act as a basis for defining indicators and methods their assessment. Determined that the level of competences and skills of employee depends on maximizing profits enterprises from their minimal costs. Found that one of the most important tasks of managers is the choice of tools to assess competence of the employee. so this requires understanding of classifications of competences of the employee socially responsible processing enterprises and allocation of their features. Allocated to different classification features of competence of the employees, the refined nature of some their and supplemented a new classification features, which are caused by the demands of modernity. The improved integrated classification of competencies adapted to the socially responsible processing enterprises, the classification characteristics of which are: in versatility (General and professional); in the field of manifestation (instrumental, interpersonal, systemic); in the subject specialization (production, managerial, financial-economic, intellectual, diagnostic, methodological, psychological and others); in the social responsibility (social, innovation, investment and others); the type of situation which applied competencies (competencies which are used to resolve the planning situation; competences, which are used for the solution of a random situation); the level of autonomy of the formation (simple, complex); cycle training (competence that arise as a result of obtaining secondary education; competences that result from higher education); during work activities (competence at an early stage of employment, competence in the later stage of work); the level of development of the employee (high, above average, average, low); place of occurrence (workplace, as a result of the trainings, seminars, courses); the periodicity of the application (periodic, lump sum). Such a classification sign, as social responsibility is separated in a separate important component.

Key words: competence, competence, classification competence, employee, social responsibility, enterprise, processing industry.

КЛАСИФІКАЦІЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦІЙ ПРАЦІВНИКА ДЛЯ СОЦІАЛЬНО-ВІДПОВІДАЛЬНИХ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ ПЕРЕРОБНОЇ ПРОМИСЛОВОСТІ

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Анотація. В статті досліджено класифікації компетенцій працівників соціально-відповідальних підприємств переробної промисловості, які виступатимуть основою для визначення показників і методів їх оцінювання. Визначено, що від рівня компетенцій та кваліфікації працівників залежить максимальне отримання прибутку підприємства з мінімальними їх витратами. З'ясовано, що одним з найважливіших завдань керівників, є вибір інструментів для оцінки компетенцій працівника тому для цього потрібне розуміння класифікацій компетенцій працівника соціально-відповідальних переробних підприємств та виділення їх за ознаками. Виокремлено різноманітні класифікаційні ознаки компетенцій працівників, уточнено сутність деяких, а також доповнено наявні новими класифікаційними ознаками, які викликані вимогами сучасності. Запропонована удосконалена комплексна класифікація компетенцій працівників адаптована до соціально-відповідальних переробних підприємств, класифікаційні ознаки якої : за універсальністю (загальні та фахові); за сферою прояву (інструментальні, міжособистісні, системні); за предметною спеціалізацією (виробничі, управлінські, фінансово-економічні, інтелектуальні, діагностичні, методологічні, психологічні та інші); за соціальною відповідальністю (соціальні, інноваційні, інвестиційні та інші); за типом ситуації для вирішення якої застосовують компетенції (компетенції, які застосовують для вирішення планової ситуації; компетенції, які застосовують для вирішення випадкової ситуації); за рівнем самостійності формування (прості, комплексні); за циклом навчальної підготовки (компетенції, які виникають внаслідок здобуття середньої освіти; компетенції, які виникають внаслідок здобуття вищої освіти); за етапом трудової діяльності (компетенції на ранньому етапі трудової діяльності, компетенції на пізньому етапі трудової діяльності); за рівнем розвитку у працівника (високий, вище середнього, середній, низький); за місцем виникнення (на робочому місці, внаслідок проходження тренінгів, семінарів, курсів тощо); за періодичністю застосування (періодичні, одноразові). Така класифікаційна ознака, як соціальна відповідальність відокремлена в окрему важливу складову.

Ключові слова: компетенція, компетентність, класифікація компетенцій, працівник, соціальна відповідальність, підприємство, переробна промисловість.

Introduction. Employees of socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry the same as in all other enterprises is an important strategic resource. The maximizing profits from their minimal costs is depends from the level of competence

and qualification of employees. The higher the level of competence, ability to react quickly to market changes and the ability to make important decisions – is the key to the high competitiveness of the products and strengthening the competitive advantages of the enterprise that affects its financial condition. That is why, in today's economy, the development of competences through professional development, training, retraining of the workers became very important.

One of the most important tasks of managers is the choice of tools to assess competence of the employee. For this you need an understanding of classifications of competences of the employee of socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry and highlight them on the grounds.

Materials and methods of research. In the course of research were used the same General scientific and special methods of research: theoretical generalization and comparison and morphological analysis – in the process of formation of conceptual-categorical apparatus of research; system analysis - to identify opportunities and justify the results of the classification of competencies of employees of socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry, whose number increases; strategic and structural-functional analysis for the formation of conceptual principles to building system of competencies employees of socially responsible processing enterprises.

Results and discussions. Scientific works domestic and foreign scientists show that the employees for efficient performance of their duties must use their expertise and competencies which are the major competitive advantage and significantly increase the productivity and depend for the professional training of specialists.

We need to consider the classification of competencies and to identify those that are belong for socially responsible processing enterprises. Such knowledge must have leaders to manage, with maximum effect in the form of profits, increased efficiency and productivity. Managers have to use other tools for understanding the matching of a worker chosen professional for enhancing or improving their level their competencies.

The order of Ministry of social policy of Ukraine «On approving the methodology of developing occupational standards» give of the General and professional competence. The General competence include: social, communicative, personal, ethical, environmental and others. Professional competencies include: specific competence, whose associated with specific knowledge in this area («*Methodology for the Development of Professional Standards*» (art. 673)).

This classification is General and comprehensive, and also adaptable and is characteristic of all national enterprises.

At the global level, we can consider the classification of the European Parliament and of the Council of Europe. In the project «Settings educational structures in Europe», aimed at the realization of the objectives of the Bologna Declaration, have a defined set of competencies as the result of the first and second cycles of learning. The work classification of competences are divided into General and special. The General competencies include instrumental, interpersonal and systemic. They are classified according to the value of the skills for the profession and level of their development after the end of the program («*On key competences for lifelong learning*» 2006).

V. M. Krivtsov and N. M. Kolisnichenko detail give a characterization of the General competencies. They believe that to instrumental competencies include cognitive, methodological, technological and linguistic abilities. Interpersonal competencies include individual skills associated with the ability to Express feelings and

to form relationships, critical reflection and ability to self-criticism, and also social skills connected with processes of social interaction and cooperation, ability to work in groups, to take social and ethical obligations. System competence is the combination of understanding, sensibility and knowledge that allows you to perceive the mutual relation between parts of a whole and appreciate the place of each of the components in the system, the ability to plan changes to improve systems and design new systems (*Odessa, Krivtsova and Kolisnichenko 2005, 87-89*).

M. S. Golovan considers the special competences on two levels – bachelor and master. On the first level the person have to show the ability to demonstrate knowledge of the foundations and history of the discipline, logically and consistently explain acquired knowledge to understand the context of the new information and give its interpretation, to demonstrate an understanding of the General culture of the discipline and the connection between its sections, to understand and use the methods of critical analyses and development of theories to properly use methods and techniques of discipline, to assess the quality of research in a particular subject area, to understand the results of observational and experimental ways of testing scientific theories. At the second level, graduates must master the subject area at the highest level, that is, have the new methods and techniques (research), to know the new theories and their interpretation; to critically monitor and reflect on the development of theory and practice; operate by independent research methods and be able to explain its results at the highest scientific level; be able to make an original contribution to the discipline in accordance with the canons of a particular subject area, for example, in the framework of a qualification; demonstrate originality and creativity; master competencies at the professional level (*Golovan 2009, 46-53*).

We support the opinion of I. Aleksev and G. Mikhailak, for that matter the lack of the proposed division of competencies of industrial employees, is the lack of a classification feature, and that the project involves two-cycle training at the bachelor's and master's levels, without paying attention to the level improving the competencies of employees at the level of postgraduate education (*Odessa, Krivtsova and Kolisnichenko 2005, 87-89*).

So, the competence of the employees of the enterprises of the processing industry classifying of depending on the scope of manifestations: instrumental, interpersonal and systemic, also depending on subject specialization: managerial, economic, mathematical, social, psychological, pedagogical, methodological, diagnostic and others.

N. V. Burda, A. V. Krushelnitskaya, D. P. Melnychuk propose to allocate the competence of employees of industrial enterprises depending on the place of their origin (*Burda 2012; Kiev, Krushelnitskaya and Melnychuk 2005, 108*).

Scientific work show us that the training of personnel and acquiring new knowledge in the form of competencies is the main factor of self-development and effective activity of the enterprise. Important in the formation of relationships between staff and managers has the knowledge, skills and abilities which are part of the competencies and give it few features, and are competitive advantages in the job market. As a result of knowledge and skills that a worker accumulates during training, they are divided into General and special. General training is keeping universal character. It is used at all levels of activity of the enterprise. Special training accumulates on a company and improves productivity and efficiency of labor. But, changing jobs reduces level of

special training, because it defeats the value of having training, seminars, courses and other types of professional training in the next leaders.

I.Oleksiv and G.Michaliak proposed us to allocate the competence depending on the location place on two kinds: competence, which we can get on the workplace, and competence, which we can get by passing the trainings, seminars, courses and the like (Oleksiv and Mikhailak 2012, 78-84).

To classify the competence of the employees of processing enterprises should be by type of situation whose solution must apply them. There are competence:

- need to resolve the planning situation;
- competencies, which are used for solving emergency situation.

Sometimes at enterprises, there are different situations, which to need addressed immediately. So, an important feature and competitive advantage of the employee, is the ability of a successful solution to planned and unforeseen problems and challenges in processing enterprises that make the administrative managers.

Generalizing the above and analyzing scientific works, we think, that for socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry it is advisable to allocate competence on universality: General (key) and professional.

European Parliament and of the Council of Europe (*On key competences for lifelong learning 2006*) to recommendation make to main competence: communicative, mathematical, computer, educational, business, socio-economic; and professional competence appropriate to divide by subject specialization – managerial, psychological, diagnostic, analytical, substantive, regulatory, research etc. It should be noted that the main competencies should be seen as a personal quality of each employee: critical thinking, creativity, initiative, dedication, teamwork, commitment to change, the execution of their duties and powers. Professional competence can be considered as special knowledge and skills to need to effectively perform the job duties. The classification of competences of employees in processing enterprises on universal grounds scientists and practitioners have developed, but, classification of competences of employees in processing enterprises on universal grounds for determine the factors that affect their development, and the formation of a system indicators their evaluation, scientists and practitioners are still not developed.

In our opinion, to socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry in addition to such competencies as: communicative, mathematical, computer, educational, business, socio-economic, managerial, psychological, diagnostic, analytical, substantive, technological, research, legal, have to apply the classification with accentuation on the level of development competences in the employee. According to this classification criterion are highlighted competency with high, average, above average and low level of development.

Employees of socially responsible companies should have a competence with a social component.

V. Hutmacher notes, that these competencies include five main competencies: political, social competence (ability to take responsibility, participate in group decision-making, in maintaining and improving democratic institutions, to resolve conflicts); competences related to life in a multicultural society (acceptance of differences, respect of others, the ability to live with people of other cultures, languages, religions); competencies related to proficiency (mastery) oral and written communication (more than one language) that are particularly important for work and social life (to avoid

social isolation); competence related to the Informatization of the society (knowledge, understanding technology, their positive and negative aspects, applications, the ability of critical thinking in relation to massmedia information and advertising); ability to learn during life as the basis of lifelong learning in the context of both personal professional and social life (*Pometun 2004, 15-25*).

Analyzing the above, in addition to the social, political competencies in each of the other four available social aspects (perception of people of other cultures, religions, languages; social communication on different levels, in the context of different technologies; secondary professional socialization), which are a manifestation of the life of the individual in society, the ability of learning during life.

So, research of different scientific views indicate that there are different grounds on which to classify the competence of the employees of processing enterprises with a comprehensive vision and understanding of their essence, the opportunities for effective management in order to maximize profits. Based on the above research, we proposed an enhanced and integrated classification of competencies adapted to the socially responsible processing enterprises. Classification characteristics: universality (General and vocational); scope of manifestation (instrumental, interpersonal, systemic); by subject specialization (production, managerial, financial-economic, intellectual, diagnostic, methodological, psychological and others); social responsibility (social, innovation, investment and others); the type of situation which applied competencies (competencies that are used to resolve the planning situation; competences, which are used for the solution of a random situation); cycle of autonomy of the formation (simple, complex); cycle training (competence that arise as a result of obtaining secondary education; competences that result from higher education); during work activities (competence at an early stage of employment, competence in the later stage of work); the level of development of the employee (high, above average, average, low); place of occurrence (workplace, as a result of the trainings, seminars, courses); the periodicity of the application (periodic, disposable). We think, that such as classification sign, as social responsibility is separated in a separate important component.

Conclusions. So, there are a number of classifications of competences of employees in a modern and foreign scientists. In order to adapt to socially responsible enterprises of the processing industry they need to add and it is a symptom of social responsibility. This classification has theoretical and practical value, because it serves as a starting point to identify factors that will influence the development of competencies; the indicators and methods by which we can assess the competence of employees, which in turn will affect the competitiveness of the enterprise, its profitability, financial condition etc.

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